

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_b_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:12:36 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	18.08	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.2759	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_b_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:12:36 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	10.93	μm	
Min:	-7.519	μm	
Max:	3.413	μm	
Size:	396211	digits	
Spacing:	0.02759	nm	
NM-points ratio:	5.539 % (498531 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:12:36 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	10.93	μm	
Size:	396211	digits	
Spacing:	0.02759	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.9279	μm	
Ssk	-3.102		
Sku	21.20		
Sp	3.407	μm	
Sv	7.525	μm	
Sz	10.93	μm	
Sa	0.5207	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.1907	%	
Smc	0.8504	μm	
Sxp	2.432	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	19.11	μm	
Str	0.7307		
Std	99.01	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.2293		
Sdr	2.263	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.04151	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.8919	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.04151	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.4220	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.7280	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.1638	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	6.521	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.6617	µm
Mean density of furrows	4182	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	44.99	°
Second direction	0.006791	°
Third direction	89.98	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	50.08	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

Information

Method Length-scale (rows)

Parameters

Value	Unit	Comment
*****		Length-scale anisotropy (Sfrac) (1.8 nm, 5°)
*****		Length-scale anisotropy (1.8 nm, 5°)

Information

Method Area-scale (four corners)

Parameters

Value	Unit	Comment
3.838		Fractal complexity
3409566	nm²	Scale of max complexity
0.6330		Heterogeneity of Asfc (3x3)
0.9538		Heterogeneity of Asfc (9x9)